

Past to Future

Towards fully paleo-informed future climate projections

Analysis of boreal forest fires

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Abstract	Charcoal records from the boreal biome of the northern hemisphere have been compiled, harmonized, and stored in a standardized format. This data compilation can be used to assess the available fire models from WP18. Analyses of the new data compilation explore frequency, severity, and synchronicity between sites and with fire proxies in Greenland ice cores.
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1. Summary

Within the scope of this deliverable, charcoal records, paleoecological indicators of long-term wildfire activity, were compiled for the boreal biome of the northern hemisphere. Data was obtained from multiple databases and private collections, quality-checked, harmonized, and stored in a standardized format. The resulting 229 boreal charcoal records were made available to the consortium via a research data management service, which enables planned data-model comparisons and linking the dataset to the upcoming data portal. Analyses based on the new data compilation were conducted, exploring past trends of biomass burning, fire frequency, and synchronicity between sites. Regionally compositing the newly compiled charcoal records uncovered Holocene trends of wildfire activity across ecologically informed boreal subregions. Pronounced differences between these trends highlight the need for testing fire models and their ability to successfully reproduce these regionally varying boreal fire histories. Using high-resolution charcoal records, fire frequencies for central and northern Europe were reconstructed over the Holocene. An explorative approach to evaluating fire event synchronicity based on these records suggests that climatic events related to changes of Atlantic circulation patterns, such as the 8.2 ka event, may create conditions conducive to increased and synchronous fire activity across central and northern Europe. An in-depth analysis of synchronicity between charcoal records is hampered by temporal uncertainties in underlying chronologies and the clear definition of charcoal peaks that represent fire events. In addition to providing the boreal data compilation, this deliverable enables various follow-up studies and provides recommendations for future research pathways within and beyond the consortium.

2. Evidence of accomplishment

2.1 Introduction | Background of the deliverable

Task 13.3, WP13, assembles data on postglacial (last 16 ka) **boreal wildfire activity as a basis for subsequent data-model comparisons** (WP18). This data foundation is generated by compiling charcoal records, paleoecological proxies for biomass burning, from the boreal biome of the northern hemisphere. Based on this data compilation, the frequency, severity, and synchronicity of fires between sites and with fire proxies in Greenland ice cores are explored. This report documents the motivation, methodological approach, and results of the analyses. It also documents the resulting data product of compiled and harmonized datasets on the postglacial boreal wildfire activity.

Boreal forests represent the largest terrestrial biome, comprising about one third of the world's tree stocks. Large areas are considered unmanaged even today (Gauthier et al., 2015). Together with extensive permafrost coverage, this makes boreal forests a terrestrial carbon reservoir of a global scale. **They are also considered a potential tipping element with global relevance for climate change**, shifting from a carbon sink to a potential carbon source (Lenton et al., 2012). Although many common boreal trees share many traits, there are important regional differences in species composition and traits. North American boreal forests, for example, include fire-embracing species such as black spruce (*Picea mariana*) or jack pine (*Pinus banksiana*), while these do not naturally occur in Siberia. In Siberia, there is a divide between East and West, with evergreen fire-avoiding coniferous trees such as Siberian cedar (*Pinus sibirica*), Scotch pine (*Pinus sylvestris*), or Siberian spruce (*Picea obovata*) dominating in the West. In the Siberian East, forests are instead dominated by deciduous fire-resisting larches (*Larix gmelinii*, *L. sibirica*, *L. cajanderi*; Wirth, 2005; Rogers et al., 2015). These are broad-scale examples of differences between boreal subregions, highlighting that despite a comparatively low biodiversity, the boreal zone is indeed quite heterogeneous in vegetation composition. This affects ecological processes and relationships, such as fire strategies and common fire regimes, but also has implications regarding ecosystem services for human societies.

Wildfires represent a key ecological disturbance factor of boreal forests, although fire regimes naturally differ between regions. Fire radiative power, a measure of fire intensity, tends to be higher in wildfires in North America compared to those in Siberia (Rogers et al., 2015). Deciduous larches of eastern Siberia are considered promoting frequent but low-intensity surface fires. In contrast, common fire-embracing evergreen tree species in North America fuel high-intensity crown fires. Despite the common notion of catastrophic fire events in the public perception, **fires fulfill an important ecological purpose within the boreal zone**. In North America, jack pine depends on intense fires to spread its seeds from serotinous cones. In eastern Siberia, low-intensity ground fires clear the dense organic layer and make way for larch seeds to reach the ground and germinate, actively supporting the rejuvenation of the forest. Fires are therefore considered an integral part of the diverse ecological dynamics in the boreal zone. However, the needle litter of larches protects the permafrost as an insulating organic layer, so that here changes in the frequency and intensity of wildfires may impact permafrost thawing (Kirilyanov et al., 2020).

Fire regimes are not static but change over time driven by climatic, environmental, or human factors. Current climate warming generally exacerbates weather conditions prone to fire ignitions, with warmer temperatures leading to a decrease in days of snow cover and an increase in fire season length. Increased growing season length and warmth can also lead to an increased buildup of flammable fuels. Warming temperatures have shown to correspond to an increased likelihood of lightning strikes, the prime ignition source in regions without much human activity (Janssen et al., 2023). The boreal zone, stretching into the high latitudes, experiences faster-than-average warming through the Arctic Amplification (Rantanen et al.,

2022). **The occurrence of extreme fire seasons, such as in Canada in 2023 with a record-breaking annually burned area of c. 150,000 km², have been partially attributed to climate change** (Jain et al., 2024). Many regions of the boreal zone now experience exceptional fire seasons in terms of area burned and fire intensity (Cunningham et al., 2024). In addition to the local threats such as intensified fire regimes, vast smoke plumes can amplify negative health and economic effects over even larger areas. For example, the extreme fire season in eastern Siberia in 2021 led to health impacts and economic losses across East Asia (Yasunari et al., 2024). **All these factors make the boreal zone a key region that is currently experiencing first-hand the impacts of climate change on wildfire regimes.**

Clearly, the nature of changing fire regimes in the boreal zone and their long-term impact on both ecology and society needs to be understood. However, as opposed to climate change, where one can rely on hundreds of years of observational records to put present changes into a long-term context, **systematic observations of wildfire activity remain limited to a few decades of satellite-based data.** While remote sensing data provide highly valuable opportunities for the study of modern fire regimes, they cannot be directly used to gain insights into long-term fire regime changes, drivers, and impacts. Instead, **paleoecological methods are required to extend the understanding of fire regime changes on centennial to millennial scales.** Preserved charcoal particles in natural archives such as lake or peat sediments represent an established proxy for changes in the amount of biomass burning through time (Whitlock and Larsen, 2001). By obtaining a sediment core, drilled through the accumulated sediment layers, and quantifying charcoal particles of various size classes within extracted samples, past changes of wildfire activity can be uncovered and compared to other proxy data documenting changes in climate, vegetation, or human activity. Depending on the nature of such a charcoal record, statistical tools can be applied to derive the timing of significant fire events, fire return intervals, and fire frequencies. Such methods thus provide an **opportunity to reconstruct and evaluate drivers and impacts of changing wildfire regimes in Earth's history,** deriving knowledge that can also be applied to current challenges.

One way in which paleoecological data on past wildfire dynamics directly benefit efforts of predicting future changes is their **ability to constrain fire models and improve confidence in simulated scenarios** (Marlon et al., 2016). Fire models exist in various conceptual forms and degrees of complexity, developed for different purposes (e.g., Hantson et al., 2016). Global fire models are used as common components of dynamic global vegetation models (DGVMs) or fully coupled Earth system models (ESMs), which enables directly linking their drivers and impacts to simulated climate or vegetation. Examples for widely used fire models include the process-based SPITFIRE (Thonicke et al., 2010), or the statistical SIMFIRE model (Knorr et al., 2014), both of which were previously coupled to DGVMs such as LPJ-GUESS (Smith et al., 2001; Lasslop et al., 2020). Previous research shows that **fire model simulations of the boreal zone may not be able to capture regionally differing trends of biomass burning** as reconstructed using paleoecological methods (Molinari et al., 2021), pointing towards the need to adapt fire model setup or parameterization. However, paleoecological data availability at the time limited the scope of the data-model comparison to selected North American and European boreal regions.

Paleoecological studies using sedimentary charcoal began with palynologists quantifying the microscopic charcoal particles they found on their pollen slides and became gradually more common during the past three decades. Therefore, microscopic charcoal is usually quantified in non-contiguous subsamples across a given sediment core. This captures general trends in fire activity, but as it is not contiguous, it cannot clearly capture individual fire events. Another approach is to analyze macroscopic charcoal particles in a contiguous sampling. Here, a sediment core chronology is used to calculate charcoal accumulation rates, thereby accounting for changes in sedimentation. Both approaches have their advantages, with **microscopic charcoal highlighting broad regional to continental-scale trends of biomass burning,** and **macroscopic charcoal emphasizing local fire activity and allowing for the identification of individual fire events** (Brown et al., 2025). New charcoal-based methods, such as the

analysis of charcoal morphologies, morphometrics, or physicochemical properties, and new statistical tools were conceived. As this type of research has recently drawn much attention, hundreds of charcoal records are now available from around the world. In the boreal zone, the distribution of charcoal records was until recently generally biased towards boreal North America and Europe, with Siberia having been especially poorly represented (Marlon et al., 2016). But **in recent years many new macro- and microscopic charcoal records have been contributed across the boreal zone**, including in Siberia. **However, the wealth of global paleoecological fire data is not efficiently organized.** Multiple databases exist with differing levels of adherence to FAIR research data principles (findability, accessibility, interoperability, reusability; Wilkinson et al., 2016). For example, some datasets may be exclusive to one database, whereas others are duplicated across multiple databases and repositories. Data quality varies between datasets, and each database stores them in different, non-standardized formats. The data upload procedure also varies, with some databases enabling user uploads, whereas others curate data via specially trained data stewards. In addition, many datasets are part of private data collections and remain missing from existing databases.

This deliverable aims at compiling the wealth of paleoecological fire data from across the boreal zone, making it available for subsequent analyses, specifically the data-model comparisons within the P2F consortium (WP18). Compiled charcoal records from different sources, such as public databases and private collections, were obtained, quality-checked, and harmonized. Additionally, analyses of the newly compiled data are provided. These analyses include **1) Holocene sub-continental-scale trends of biomass burning**, with comparisons of regional trends across the boreal zone, and **2) Detailed comparison of fire events in boreal vegetation types of central and northern Europe**, exploring the detectability synchronous events indicating severity.

2.2 Content of the deliverable

Compilation of boreal charcoal records

In order to **compile paleoecological data on long-term boreal wildfire activity for use in data-model comparisons**, macroscopic and microscopic charcoal records were obtained from the following sources: the Global Paleofire Database (GPD; Power et al., 2010), the Reading Paleofire Database (RPD; Harrison et al., 2022), and private collections.

GPD data were manually extracted for all regions broadly overlapping with the boreal zone via the website interface (<https://www.paleofire.org/home>) on September 6, 2025. These data were then handled in R (v.4.5.1; R Core Team, 2025) and subset by coordinates overlapping with a boreal and tundra ecoregions shapefile (RESOLVE Ecoregions 2017; Dinerstein et al., 2017). The tundra ecoregion was included as a spatial buffer, since a few charcoal records were located in boreal-tundra transition zones and would not have been captured with only the boreal ecoregion shapefile. Datasets were further filtered according to a set of quality criteria. Extracted charcoal records reported as counts or concentrations were transformed into influxes, and all data was stored in a standardized format (tables in .csv file format, each containing columns for depth, age, and influx; n = 133).

The whole **RPD** SQL database (RPDv1b.sql) was downloaded via the website (<https://doi.org/10.17864/1947.000345>) on September 17, 2025, and subsequently handled in R using the “RMySQL” package (Ooms et al., 2025). Charcoal records were subset to only include appropriate depositional contexts (“lake”, “bog sediment”, “small hollow”), measurement methods (“Sieved”, “Pollen slide”, “Charcoal particles identified by imaging software”), and units (“influx”, “concentration”, “count”, “raw count”), and by coordinates overlapping with the same boreal and tundra ecoregions shapefile. The remaining records were subset according to coordinate pairs and site names that were not already

included via data initially obtained from the GPD. Some records stored in the RPD contain the original author's age information and/or ages from retroactively updated chronologies (see Harrison et al., 2022). Here, where available, age information from the original authors were used, otherwise the updated chronologies were selected. Finally, a manual check was conducted to discard unsuitable charcoal records (e.g., missing age information, records consisting of few individual samples), before data reported as counts or concentrations were transformed into influxes, and all data was stored in the same standardized file format (n = 46).

Charcoal records from known **private collections** not yet available via either database were added to the analysis in the same standardized format (n = 50). These collections include charcoal records that were presented and evaluated in published literature but not yet submitted to either database and were provided by consortium partners and contributors (Tallinn University of Technology, National Resources Canada, University of Utah). In total, this approach **resulted in a compilation of 229 harmonized datasets of charcoal accumulation rates across the boreal zone.**

The compiled **dataset of harmonized boreal charcoal records is available for download** for consortium members and contributors via the Yoda research data management service of Utrecht University (<https://doi.org/10.24416/UU01-ULL0TO>; Glückler et al., 2026). In this folder, all individual harmonized charcoal records derived for inclusion in the boreal data compilation can be found in their standardized format (tables in .csv file format, each containing columns for depth, age, and influx). Additionally, a metadata file is provided, specifying information such as site name, coordinates, and source of each charcoal record. The folder on Yoda should be considered as a temporary holding tank for the data compilation, enabling exchanges within the consortium and among contributors. It can also be linked to the upcoming data portal (WP7). However, public access to this temporary holding tank remains restricted until original charcoal records from private collections can be made fully available according to the aforementioned FAIR principles. The **efficient storage of charcoal records according to these principles is currently under development for the Neotoma Paleoeology Database** (Williams et al., 2018; see also European COST-Action CA23116 “PalaeOpen” at <https://palaeopen.github.io/> and Dietze et al., 2024), with the goal of making the GPD a new constituent database of Neotoma. Once a data deposition structure according to the FAIR principles has been established for Neotoma, the charcoal records from private collections will be made publicly available there. By doing so, **this deliverable supports ongoing efforts to make paleoecological charcoal data FAIR.** Current developments of the charcoal community associated with Neotoma include a standardized upload template with controlled vocabulary. Once the data is uploaded to Neotoma, it will benefit from extensive metadata, the ability to store multiple versions of chronological data, and an associated digital object identifier (DOI) for individual datasets. In this way, the curation of the data will be guaranteed beyond the use within the P2F project consortium.

Examination of Holocene boreal fire histories

To examine Holocene trends of biomass burning within the new data compilation, the charcoal records were subset by their locations into the subregions of western (-180 to -120°E), central (-120 to -90°E), and eastern (-90 to 30°E) North America, Europe (-30 to 60°E), western Siberia (60 to 100°E) and eastern Siberia (100 to 180°E). These regions were chosen to broadly reflect the ecological differences within the boreal biome, such as the boundary between evergreen and deciduous forests in Siberia. For each subregion, charcoal composite curves were created following established methods (e.g., Marlon et al., 2016), using the “paleofire” package in R (Blarquez et al., 2014). The base period for standardization between charcoal records was set as 200 to 10,000 years BP for all subregions except western Siberia, where data availability still remains lower, and a shorter base period of 200 to 4500 years BP was used. This way, **composite curves, representing the regional trends of past levels of biomass burning, were created and plotted**

for each subregion (Figure 1). Fire proxies recorded in the RECAP ice core from eastern Greenland (levoglucosan, black carbon, and ammonium; Segato et al., 2021) are used to provide an explorative comparison between the new compilation of boreal wildfire activity and more broad-scale, hemispheric trends captured by the ice shield archive. This comparison has the potential to be further expanded thanks to the involvement of consortium partners (University of Copenhagen) in active work on other deep Greenland ice cores (WP9).

Figure 1: Overview of charcoal composite curves for the whole boreal biome (top, grey) and separated by boreal subregions (left and right, colored), based on the new data compilation, and comparison to an ice core record of fire proxies (Segato et al., 2021; bottom). Charcoal composite curves are shown as the median (line) and 95% confidence interval (shaded area). Boreal forest extent shown according to the RESOLVE Ecoregions 2017 (Dinerstein et al., 2017).

An examination of the boreal data compilation shows that data availability has indeed improved in recent years (for comparison see Marlon et al., 2013), yet **some remaining regions benefitting from further charcoal record contributions can also be identified** (Figure 1). Western North America is represented by 35 charcoal records, central North America by 30, and eastern North America by 67. Europe is represented by 63 charcoal records. Western Siberia includes 8 charcoal records, and eastern Siberia includes 26. Additional effort should therefore mainly be placed on compiling and generating charcoal records from western Siberia. However, coverage within individual subregions is not equally distributed and thus also needs to be considered, with charcoal records currently lacking in the easternmost regions of North America (i.e., Newfoundland and Labrador, eastern Québec), the Russian regions of Europe, southern Siberian boreal forests other than the vicinity of Lake Baikal, or the Pacific Siberian Far East (i.e., Kamchatka, Magadan, Khabarovsk, Sakhalin).

The boreal data compilation by subregion highlights regional differences (Figure 1). While the trend for western North America indicates increasing biomass burning throughout the past 10,000 years, central North America saw a decreasing trend after a Mid-Holocene maximum around 6000 years BP. These results are broadly comparable to previous regional studies (Kelly et al., 2013; Nesbitt et al., 2025). Eastern

North America, on the other hand, displays a more stagnant picture and decreasing wildfire activity during the past millennium. Here, Marlon et al. (2016) reported a contrasting result of increasing biomass burning during the last c. 3000 years. These contrasting trends may be caused by the increased number of available charcoal records in the present analysis, or by differences in the charcoal record selection, harmonization, and compositing procedure. The European trend shows a maximum in the Early Holocene, followed by decreasing levels of biomass burning and another maximum within the last 1000 years. Western Siberia is characterized by an increasing trend of biomass burning over the past c. 2000 years. Eastern Siberia, on the other hand, displays a clear Early Holocene maximum (c. 10,000 years BP), followed by a decrease and another maximum around 8000 years BP. From c. 7000 to 6000 years BP, the level of biomass burning declines and fluctuates on a lower level until recent times. A visual comparison to fire proxy trends in the RECAP ice core of eastern Greenland, available for the past c. 5000 years (Figure 1, bottom), shows no immediate correspondence to one of the boreal subregion's charcoal composite curves. However, recorded trends of black carbon concentration do seem to mirror the composite curve of all combined boreal regions (Figure 1, top). Varying production pathways and spatial sources of the different fire proxies, proxy taphonomy, and processes that form the ice core which are unique to ice shield archives need to be considered in such a comparison, and in-depth analyses will be supported by newly established connections to the University of Copenhagen and WP9 within the P2F project. **The boreal data compilation now enables follow-up research on in-depth comparisons between these archives and regions, facilitated for example by wind field modelling to estimate fire proxy source regions within the boreal zone and targeted compositing of corresponding charcoal records.**

Comparison of fire events in boreal vegetation types of central and northern Europe

To explore the possibility of assessing wildfire synchronicity between sites, a subset of high-resolution macroscopic charcoal records from Fennoscandia and Central Europe was analyzed. Before assessing synchronicity, the potentially synchronous fire events first need to be identified, and this **statistical analysis necessitates contiguously sampled charcoal records of high temporal resolution**. The chosen region is exceptionally well covered relative to the global distribution of charcoal records, thus providing a high number of suitable datasets. The northern boreal zone was here extended south into the hemiboreal zone of Fennoscandia and the Baltics. Higher elevation sites with boreal-like vegetation in central and eastern Europe (Czech Republic, Slovakia, Romania) were included to increase the number of available charcoal records. Selection was supported by consortium partners and contributors (Charles University, Tallinn University of Technology). Constraints for the selection included a high median temporal resolution below 50 years per sample, and the temporal coverage of the 8.2 ka event, when a strong climatic excursion resulted in documented changes in European forest composition (Tinner and Lotter, 2001). The climatic event was triggered by meltwater pulses from the Laurentide Ice Shield into the Atlantic (Thomas et al., 2007) and is suspected of having affected European wildfire regimes. Suitable charcoal records outside of the boreal regions covered by the new data compilation introduced above were obtained via Neotoma (Williams et al., 2018) and the RPD (Harrison et al., 2022). A total of 19 high-resolution charcoal records were selected for inclusion in the analysis (see Table 1).

Table 1: Selected subset of high-resolution charcoal records for the explorative analysis of fire synchronicity between sites. Charcoal records obtained from the RPD (Reading Paleofire Database; Harrison et al., 2022) can be identified within the SQL database via the field "ID_ENTITY".

Site name	Latitude	Longitude	Source	DOI or ID	Related publication
Lövnäs Arjeplog	66.310833	17.900833	RPD	ID_ENTITY = 577	Carcaillet et al. (2007)
Lattok Arjeplog	65.956944	18.345	RPD	ID_ENTITY = 135	Carcaillet et al. (2007)
Klotjärnen	61.82125	16.40472	RPD	ID_ENTITY = 738	Brown and Giesecke (2014)
Holtjärnen	60.65189	14.92652	RPD	ID_ENTITY = 737	Brown and Giesecke (2014)
Lake Bricu	57.115374	25.870619	RPD	ID_ENTITY = 1583	Steinberga and Stivrins (2021)
Storasjö	56.93333	15.26667	RPD	ID_ENTITY = 1406	Olsson et al. (2010)
Lielais Svētiņu	56.76	27.14912	RPD	ID_ENTITY = 2480	Feurdean et al. (2017b)

Rašeliniště Jizery	50.861706	15.301881	RPD	ID_ENTITY = 2248	Bobek et al. (2019)
Velké ohbí	50.604057	16.127125	RPD	ID_ENTITY = 2250	Bobek et al. (2019)
Vlček	50.039798	12.731939	RPD	ID_ENTITY = 2251	Bobek et al. (2019)
Tajga	50.0261	12.680355	RPD	ID_ENTITY = 2254	Bobek et al. (2019)
Černé jezero	49.17901238	13.18304717	Neotoma	10.21233/DZKP-7N31	Mateo Beneito et al. (2024)
Popradské pleso	49.153142	20.079368	Neotoma	10.21233/G61Y-0G82	Carter et al. (2020)
Prášilské jezero	49.07525199	13.40005431	RPD	ID_ENTITY = 2194	Carter et al. (2018)
Stará Jímka	49.068764	13.402947	RPD	ID_ENTITY = 2249	Bobek et al. (2019)
Pěkná	48.840704	13.93508	Neotoma	10.21233/3WPP3-X634	Kraklow et al. (2024)
Poiana Știol	47.59	24.8119	RPD	ID_ENTITY = 1650	Feurdean et al. (2017a)
Tăul Muced	47.5739	24.5446	RPD	ID_ENTITY = 1863	Feurdean et al. (2017a)
Lake Stiucii	46.97	23.8997	RPD	ID_ENTITY = 1655	Feurdean et al. (2013)

Individual fire events, and with them fire frequency, can be derived from a high-resolution charcoal record by following a commonly applied statistical decomposition approach (Higuera et al., 2009; Glückler et al., 2021; Figure 2): First, using the author’s original chronology, charcoal accumulation rates (CHAR), interpolated to median temporal resolution, were calculated in R using the “paleofire” package (Blarquez et al., 2014). A locally estimated scatterplot smoothing was used to determine a low-frequency “background component” of the charcoal record, representing long-term trends of biomass burning and secondary charcoal input. By subtracting the background component from CHAR, a high-frequency “peak component” was created, representing short-term events of charcoal deposition. All peaks above a set threshold (determined by the 99th percentile of the noise distribution of two Gaussian distributions fitted into the peak component histogram) were subsequently identified as “fire events”, distinguished in quality by a signal-to-noise index (Kelly et al., 2011). The term “fire event” is used here while considering the possibility of multiple fires contributing to a given charcoal peak, according to the decadal-scale temporal resolution of the charcoal records. The regional average fire frequency was estimated by counting the number of identified fire events across non-overlapping 100-year bins for all charcoal records. **To assess the synchronicity of fire events between sites, the number of charcoal records contributing with at least one fire event to a 100-year wide bin was determined.** Since both fire frequency and the measure of synchronicity relate to the regional wildfire activity of the studied region, a composite curve of regional biomass burning was created as a reference, following the composition approach outlined before.

Figure 2: Exemplary macroscopic charcoal record from Holtjärnen, central Sweden (Brown and Giesecke, 2014). Charcoal accumulation rate (CHAR; black line) with background component (orange line) and statistically identified peaks representing fire events (vertical lines). Green fire event lines lie above a signal-to-noise index threshold, whereas grey fire event lines lie below it and are thus less clearly separated from lower amplitude of variability.

The results indicate that **regional fire frequency across all 19 charcoal records was high around 10,500 years BP and from c. 7000 to 8500 years BP** (Figure 3B). Between c. 3000 to 6000 years BP, low fire frequencies were recorded, with a slight increase towards 1000 years BP. Since then, fire frequencies remained on an intermediate level. Identified significant peaks within the individual charcoal record’s peak components, interpreted as fire events, yield an **average fire return interval of 225 ± 124 years** (mean ±

standard deviation) across all 19 sites. The longest average fire return interval at an individual site is reconstructed at the northernmost charcoal record, Lövnäs Arjeplog in northern Sweden (505 years). Increasing fire return intervals with higher latitudes are generally expected as an effect of decreasing insolation, shortened fire seasons, lower fuel load, and a corresponding increase in surface moisture retention (Kharuk et al., 2016). The shortest average fire return interval at an individual site was reconstructed at Lielais Svētiņu, Latvia (61 years).

Figure 3: Left side: Map of central and northern Europe, indicating the location of selected high-resolution charcoal records. Dark green shading indicates the present-day boreal forest extent according to the RESOLVE Ecoregions 2017 (Dinerstein et al., 2017). Right side: Holocene fire activity across all selected charcoal records. **A:** Composite curve (median) of charcoal records to indicate regional trends of biomass burning. Shaded area represents the 95% confidence interval, using the distribution of 1000 bootstrapped replicates from the binned records. **B:** Number of fire events identified per 100-year bin across all sites to indicate regional average fire frequency. Shaded area represents the interquartile range. **C:** Number of sites contributing at least one fire event per 100-year bin as a measure of synchronicity across the study region. **D:** Total number of sites with charcoal data available per 100-year bin.

When searching for synchronous wildfire activity with charcoal records contributing at least one fire event per 100-year bin, the bin from 8050 to 8150 years BP records the highest value ($n = 11$ out of 19; Figure 3C). The same bin also records the highest absolute number of fire events across all charcoal records ($n = 28$). While in the preceding Early Holocene, a decreasing coverage of charcoal records limits this analysis, the record high number of contributing sites in the bin centered on 8100 years BP indicates that during this time more than any other since, fire events occurred across the studied region of Europe. The timing notably corresponds to the termination period of the 8.2 ka event as recorded by oxygen isotopes in Greenland ice cores (Thomas et al., 2007). As a clearly delineated, decadal- to centennial-scale climatic event, among its described consequences for the mid- to high-latitudes of Europe were decreased temperature and humidity (Thomas et al., 2007), and more recently, simulations indicated potentially long-lasting impacts on vegetation composition (Li et al., 2019). However, effects on temperature and humidity may have been regionally heterogeneous due to effects on atmospheric circulation patterns (e.g., Perşoiu et al., 2017). A previous study evaluating charcoal records from central and northern Europe, including some of the records analyzed here, also found the highest levels of biomass burning across all sites in

relation to the 8.2 ka event (Florescu et al., 2019). Together, these results point towards the **climatic conditions created by the 8.2 ka event facilitating the most synchronous increases in wildfire activity** across the studied region during potentially the whole Holocene. This result may have **implications for the impact of the widely discussed shutdown of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) with continued climate change** (e.g., Drijfhout et al., 2025), since the 8.2 ka event can be considered a key potential paleoclimatic analogue for such a scenario.

To **assess potential differences between charcoal records in the northern and southern subregions**, the analysis shown in Figure 3 was applied to the charcoal records from both subregions separately (Figure 4). This approach reduces the number of available high-resolution charcoal records per subregion (northern sites: $n = 7$; southern sites: $n = 12$), but it shows that the combined signal of synchronicity (Figure 3C) is dominated by high values among southern sites around 8000 years BP, whereas the northern sites show their highest value of synchronicity rather within the last millennium (Figure 4C). Regional trends of biomass burning also differ between the two subregions (Figure 4A), with the northern sites showing an increasing trend over the Holocene, especially since c. 3000 years BP. In contrast, the southern sites display a decreasing trend over the Holocene. However, such composite curves benefit from including as many charcoal records from a region as possible, making the curve for the European subregion in Figure 1 preferable for an analysis of regional Holocene trends of biomass burning in the boreal region. The composite curves shown here for the northern and southern subregions should instead be viewed as a reference to the fire frequency and synchronicity, derived from the same high-resolution subset of charcoal records. Still, the differences between the northern boreal/hemiboreal and the southern boreal-like sites indicate that **climatic impacts on fire regimes, and likely their historical fuel sources, were heterogeneous across central/eastern and northern Europe**.

Figure 4: Holocene fire activity across all selected charcoal records, separated into northern and southern regions. **A:** Composite curve (median) of charcoal records to indicate regional trends of biomass burning. Shaded area represents the 95% confidence interval, using the distribution of 1000 bootstrapped replicates from the binned records. **B:** Number of fire events identified per 100-year bin across all sites to indicate regional average fire frequency. Shaded area represents the interquartile range. **C:** Number of sites contributing at least one fire event per 100-year bin as a measure of synchronicity across the respective region. **D:** Total number of sites with charcoal data available per 100-year bin.

Determining synchronicity of fire events between sites in more depth rests on the **ability to identify outstanding and clearly delineated peaks in multiple charcoal records and comparing their timing**. This timing is controlled by the underlying chronological data of a sediment core, based on age dating information from methods such as radiocarbon age dating, and a statistical age-depth modeling procedure. To test the overlap probability between specific fire events, two of the charcoal records closest to each other were selected (Černé jezero and Prášílské jezero, Czech Republic; c. 20 km distance; Mateo Beneito et al., 2024; Carter et al., 2018). Close vicinity between charcoal records was assumed to increase the likelihood of capturing the same fire event at both sites. However, while both charcoal records meet the condition of high temporal resolution below 50 years per sample, the identified charcoal peaks were found to be not clearly delineated and instead stretching across multiple decades with a period of an onset, the actual peak, and a period of termination. Such a pattern, irrespective of its ecological cause, does not lend these charcoal records to a fine-scale analysis of synchronicity. Instead, we selected the next-closest pair of charcoal records (Lattok Arjeplog and Lövnäs Arjeplog, Sweden; c. 40 km; Carcaillet et al., 2007). Both records display clearly delineated peaks identified as fire events, with a high signal-to-noise index. To account for uncertainty in the timing of the fire events, chronologies for both charcoal records were recalculated in the Bayesian age-depth modeling software OxCal (v4.4; Bronk Ramsey, 2008, 2009; Bronk Ramsey and Lee, 2013), using up-to-date calibration curves (Reimer et al., 2020). By using OxCal, it was further made possible to extract 100 individual age-depth model ensemble runs, so **the timing of a given fire event could be described not just by a singular median age estimate, but instead by a more realistic uncertainty distribution** of various age estimates for the corresponding sediment core depth. The degree of distribution overlap between the uncertainty distributions of fire event pairs between the two sites was calculated to test the impact of chronological uncertainty on asserting synchronicity.

Figure 5: Exemplary comparison of the age uncertainty around two identified fire events (vertical lines) from the close-by sites Lattok Arjeplog and Lövnäs Arjeplog (Carcaillet et al., 2007), respectively. Distribution polygons represent 100 ensemble runs of the Bayesian age modeling software OxCal (Bronk Ramsey, 2009). Despite a high degree of overlap between the distributions, multi-centennial uncertainties persist that limit the ability to assess direct synchronicity.

The distribution overlap between age determinations of the temporally closest fire events reached above 80% (Figure 5), indicating that the probability ranges for the true ages of these fire events are indeed similar. However, a high degree of distribution overlap does not necessarily indicate synchronicity between both fire events. For that, the probability for both fire events to lie within the same year or range of years needs to be determined from these distributions. As evident in Figure 5, the uncertainty distributions from age-depth modeling still stretch across multiple hundreds of years. Based on this result, two main issues for an in-depth analysis of synchronicity between sites can now be identified: Large uncertainty ranges in a charcoal record chronology, and the presence of charcoal peaks that are not clearly delineated. This leads to the conclusion that **a deeper, fine-scale analysis of synchronicities between fire events is technically feasible, but requires suitable charcoal records that must meet the following conditions:**

1) an archive with high sedimentation rates facilitating a high temporal resolution, 2) a systematic age determination approach using, for example, dense radiocarbon age dating or varve counts, if available, and 3) high density sampling for contiguous charcoal analysis, yielding clearly delineated peaks. Besides an initial broad-scale analysis of boreal forest fire synchronicities, the present data analysis lays out the statistical tools that can be employed to suitable records for more in-depth analyses going forward.

Institutions contributing to this deliverable

All analyses featured within this report were conducted exclusively at Utrecht University, including data compilation, harmonization, evaluation, visualization, and deposition. Individual datasets for the compilation of boreal charcoal records were provided to Utrecht University by other consortium partners and external contributors (Tallinn University of Technology, National Resources Canada, University of Utah). The comparison of fire events in boreal vegetation types of central and northern Europe was supported by conceptual discussions of Utrecht University with consortium partners and external contributors (Charles University, Tallinn University of Technology). The compilation of harmonized boreal charcoal records is hosted as a data package on the research data management system of Utrecht University.

2.3 Conclusion and possible impact

The data compilation of harmonized charcoal records from the boreal biome of the northern hemisphere has been generated, documented, and made available as a key result of this deliverable. Within the consortium, the data compilation is now available for testing fire models from WP18 and can be linked to the upcoming data portal from WP7. The data compilation is used for follow-up studies, such as an in-depth comparison to fire proxies in ice core archives from WP9. Regarding the impact on the research community, the data compilation actively benefits ongoing external efforts of migrating data into an efficient database structure for the deposition of charcoal records (i.e., European COST-Action CA23116 “PalaeOpen”). Explorative analyses based on the new data compilation demonstrate that it is enabling the most comprehensive comparisons of long-term wildfire activity between boreal subregions to date, which will be further developed into a scientific publication. The differing Holocene trends uncovered here reinforce the need for data-model comparisons, as planned within the consortium, to test whether state-of-the-art fire models can reproduce these differences. An explorative assessment of fire event synchronicity between sites demonstrates the technical feasibility of such an approach. Results indicate the precedence of climatic events to trigger increased and synchronized fire activity across central Europe. Remaining issues currently prohibiting an in-depth analysis of synchronicity could be identified, followed by recommendations for a successful application going forward.

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3. Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication of the results

3.1 Impact within the consortium

This deliverable of WP13 (D13.3) provides a compilation of boreal charcoal records, required for testing state-of-the-art fire models in WP18 (T18.3). The report provides initial analyses on long-term trends of biomass burning across the boreal zone, fire frequencies and synchronicities in central and northern Europe. These are stimulating further cooperation with other consortium members including comparisons to ice core data (WP9). The dataset is available for linking to the upcoming data portal (WP7). The timing of this deliverable has been adjusted and expedited to improve its alignment with WP18 (see section 4).

3.2 Impact within the wider scientific community

The initial analysis of the compilation of boreal charcoal records provides a strong improvement over earlier analyses, now clearly revealing different regional as well as continental trends. The planned data-model comparisons will address whether these differences are due to the regional differences in vegetation or climate. Results will be presented in publications and conferences. It strengthens the interaction between paleoecologists and modeling communities.

Scientific Publications

<i>Title</i>	<i>Author(s)</i>	<i>DOI</i>	<i>Status (in prep, submitted, under review, accepted)</i>
Holocene wildfire history across boreal ecoregions	Ramesh Glückler, Kendrick Brown, Mitchell Power, Anneli Poska, Thomas Giesecke	-	in prep.
Evaluating the synchronicity of Holocene fire events in Central and Northern Europe	Ramesh Glückler, Anneli Poska, Thomas Giesecke, Petr Kuneš	-	in prep.

Data

Description of the dataset	DOI	URL to repository
Compilation of harmonized boreal charcoal records in standardized format	https://doi.org/10.24416/UU01-ULL0TO	https://public.yoda.uu.nl/geo/UU01/ULL0TO.html

Other output

Type of activity (e.g. talk, poster, meeting etc.)	Details (where, who, what)	Target Audience + estimate on number of people reached	Impact Area
Poster	P2F General Assembly, November 5-7, 2025, in	Scientific community; ca. 80 people reached	Strengthen research networks

	Utrecht, Netherlands (Ramesh Glückler)		
Talk (scheduled)	BeNeLux Geography Conference, April 8-10, 2026, in Leuven, Belgium (Ramesh Glückler)	Scientific community; ca. 50 people reached	Strengthen research networks; Enhance scientific impact of P2F findings
Talk and poster (scheduled)	International Boreal Forest Research Association Conference, August 24-28, 2026, in Quebec City, Canada (Ramesh Glückler)	Scientific community; Policymakers; Local communities disproportionately impacted by climate change; ca. 100 people reached	Strengthen research networks; Enhance scientific impact of P2F findings

3.3 Impact beyond the scientific community

Boreal forest fires are intensifying under ongoing climate change and put local communities at risk, yet a lacking long-term understanding of fire regime changes currently limits sustainable and resilient management perspectives. This deliverable provides policymakers with a long-term perspective on wildfire regimes that goes beyond limited satellite records and offers insights into how abrupt climate transitions - such as changes in Atlantic overturning circulation - may trigger synchronous fire activity in Europe. By using the past to improve the accuracy of state-of-the-art fire models, this work can support more robust, evidence-based climate and fire management policy formulation.

Activities

Type of activity (e.g. press release, social media, workshop etc.)	Details (where, who, what)	Target Audience + estimate on number of people reached	Impact Area
Workshop (scheduled)	European COST-Action CA23116 “PalaeOpen” workshop on long-term fire risk, April 27-29, 2026, in Zaragoza, Spain (Ramesh Glückler)	Policymakers; ca. 30 people reached	Develop researcher’s skills in public engagement or policy; Strengthen research networks

3.4 Future impact

Publications planned based on this deliverable include scientific publications, poster presentations, and talks (see activities scheduled under section 3.2). A workshop related to the European COST-Action CA23116 “PalaeOpen” in April 2026 will offer an opportunity to engage directly with relevant stakeholders and communicate research related to this deliverable. The new compilation of data adds to ongoing efforts of making datasets open and FAIR as part of efforts of the ongoing European COST-Action CA23116 “PalaeOpen”. Data currently not openly available will be made accessible through the paleoecological database Neotoma. Neotoma is currently being developed to curate the global proxy data for past fire histories and this deliverable is contributing to this process.

4. Changes with respect to the DoA (Description of Action)

The schedule of WP13, including the delivery date of D13.3, was amended compared to the original DoA. Several reasons necessitated an optimization of the WP13 schedule: WP13 postdoctoral researcher Ramesh Glückler (responsible for T13.1, T13.2, T13.3) started on September 1, 2025, six months later than initially planned, and no postdoctoral researcher was yet hired within WP18, which is set to closely cooperate with WP13. The successful hop-on proposal by the Estonian partners (newly added T13.5) added further reason to optimize the schedule within WP13. For these reasons, it was decided for WP13 postdoctoral researcher Ramesh Glückler to first work on T13.3, a subject in which he already holds prior expertise, enabling him to expedite progress towards D13.3 in February 2026 and thus prepare the data later needed by the postdoctoral researcher of WP18. T13.1, previously scheduled for M13-M20 (March to October 2026) with D13.1 due in M18 (August 2026), is now scheduled for M25-39 (March 2027 to May 2028) with D13.1 due in M36 (February 2028). T13.2, previously scheduled for M21-M39 (November 2026 to February 2028) with D13.2 due in M36 (February 2028), is now scheduled for M13-24 (March 2026 to February 2027) with D13.2 due in M24 (February 2027). These changes with respect to the DoA facilitate the successful preparation of WP13 deliverables while improving alignment with WP18 and the newly added T13.5.